

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

I hope you will like this issue with a mixture of quite different topics! The next three (!) issues are going to be special issues, each containing the best papers of three conferences to be held in May, June and July respectively. They will also be available in printed form for conference participants: we hope this will be good advertisement for J.UCS, and will help to expand our ever increasing readership.

Please, make sure that your university or organisation also subscribes to J.UCS: For US \$100.- a year access for all faculty and students is quite a good deal I believe! And do keep supporting J.UCS by submitting papers and spreading the word about J.UCS.

Also, if you are interested in joining the editorial board do contact me at hmaurer@iicm.edu - we still want to enlarge the editorial board, particularly in applied areas of computer science.

All the best,

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